

Unveiling the Flow: A survey on the equipment and functioning of Combined Sewer Overflows.

The majority of communities in Europe have combined sewer systems. In a combined sewer system, both wastewater and stormwater flow through the same pipes. During heavy rain events, the combined flow of wastewater and stormwater can exceed the capacity of the pipes. To address this, approved outfalls are strategically placed as relief points during wet weather. These outfalls release untreated or partially treated stormwater and wastewater into nearby water bodies, and these releases are termed Combined Sewer Overflows (CSOs).

The goal of this short survey is to understand

- what, if any, CSO performance data (e.g. spill frequencies and duration) are available at utilities
- for which purpose they are being used
- the motivation of different stakeholders [operators and regulators (academia, consultants)] to publish performance indicators on CSO (or not)

Dear wastewater professionals,

as part of the EU project "Collaborative Urban Drainage Labs" (Co-UDLabs), we are researching the availability and use of data to evaluate the performance of urban drainage systems. We are particularly interested in the availability of key figures, such as the functioning of combined sewer overflows (CSO), in the context of "Open Government Data".

The survey can be completed conveniently online and takes 10-15 minutes, depending on the size and tasks of your company. Please complete one form per drainage system, if possible. If your organization manages several or many, please provide the info for one or two typical systems. We know wastewater systems vary widely; please skip questions not relevant or interpretable for your country.

If necessary, please forward this questionnaire to the responsible person in your organization. Your information will be stored anonymously and external parties will not have access to your answers.

Thank you for your participation, your input is very important to our efforts to improve drainage planning and environmental protection.

If you have any questions or need assistance, please do not hesitate to contact us at contact@co-udlabs.eu.

Best regards, in the name of the Co-UDLab partners,

Elodie Brelot (GRAIE) and Jörg Rieckermann (Eawag)

P.S.: An initial synthesis of the survey will be discussed in the second half of 2024. If you provide us with your contact details, we will be happy to inform you of the results.

There are 48 questions in this survey.

In what year was your organization founded? *

❗ Only numbers may be entered in this field.

Please write your answer here:

How many people does your organization employ today?

❗ Only numbers may be entered in this field.

Please write your answer here:

How many communities or municipalities do you service? *

❗ Only numbers may be entered in this field.

Please write your answer here:

Is there a managing director in your utility or wastewater association?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

How do you assess the operational freedoms of your organization vis-à-vis the municipalities?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 1
 2
 3
 4
 5

This questions concerns operational independence and decision making.

How far do you agree with this statement:

Our association can operate without unnecessary bureaucratic constraints for efficient decision-making and streamlined operations. This involves making independent decisions aligned with the association's mission, setting strategies, policies, and goals without external influence.,

1= not at all

5 = completely

How do you evaluate the level of autonomy your organization has vis-à-vis the municipalities concerning governance?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- 1
- 2
- 3
- 4
- 5

This questions concerns financial independence and governance.

How far do you agree with this statement:

Our organization manages finances independently, generates revenue, allocates budgets, and seeks funding without compromising independence or core values, ensuring sustainability. It has capacity to manage internal affairs, establish operational procedures, and maintain checks and balances for effective self-regulation.

1= not at all

5 = completely

What is the total area A [ha] of the association's catchment area?

! Only numbers may be entered in this field.

Please write your answer here:

Provide the total area in hectares

What is the size of the reduced area A_{red} [hared] connected to the WWTP in the association's catchment area?

❗ Only numbers may be entered in this field.

Please write your answer here:

(Reduced area A_{red} = runoff coefficient ψ · Catchment area (A))

What facilities does your utility or wastewater association operate in addition to the WWTP?

❗ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- The WWTP (no stormwater basins, no sewerage)
- Combined sewer overflows (CSO) owned by the communities or municipalities
- Combined sewer overflows (CSO) owned by the organization
- Shares of the sewerage system owned by the municipalities
- Shares of the sewerage system owned by the organization

How many Combined sewer overflows (CSO) does your wastewater association operate?

❗ Only numbers may be entered in this field.

Please write your answer here:

Has there been a rehabilitation of a combined sewer overflow (CSO) in the last 5 years?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was greater than or equal to '1' at question '10 [NCSOs]' (How many Combined sewer overflows (CSO) does your wastewater association operate?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

Are there any investments planned for the rehabilitation of a combined sewer overflow (CSO) in the next 5 years?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was greater than or equal to '1' at question '10 [NCSOs]' (How many Combined sewer overflows (CSO) does your wastewater association operate?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

How many pumping stations does your wastewater association operate?

🚫 Only numbers may be entered in this field.

Please write your answer here:

Below you can see a selection of variables and derived quantities that can be measured on Combined sewer overflows (CSO). Please tick the measured variables that your wastewater association records.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was greater than or equal to '1' at question '10 [NCSOs]' (How many Combined sewer overflows (CSO) does your wastewater association operate?)

🗨️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Carry-on flows to the WWTP [l/s]
- Water level in the combined sewer overflow [m]
- Spill duration
- Spill frequency (spills/year)
- Overflow volume

Other:

The following question concerns monitoring on combined sewer overflows. By measuring instruments we mean, for example:

- Overflow detectors
- Sensors to measure water depth, level or water quality
- etc.

How many of your combined sewer overflows are equipped with at least one such sensor device?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was greater than or equal to '1' at question '10 [NCSOs]' (How many Combined sewer overflows (CSO) does your wastewater association operate?)

❗ Only numbers may be entered in this field.

Please write your answer here:

How many permanent rain gauges does your wastewater association operate?

❗ Only numbers may be entered in this field.

Please write your answer here:

How is the water level/spill data transmitted by the measuring devices?

🚫 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- About fiber optics
- Via fixed landline/a copper cable/cable telemetry
- Wireless via GSM (mobile network)
- Wireless via LoRaWAN (low-energy radio)
- The measurement data is recorded on site, read out manually and can be stored on a physical storage medium (e.g. USB stick) and taken along

Other:

From how many installations are the water level/spill data transmitted directly to the process control system (DCS) of the WWTP?

🚫 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- None
- From some
- Of most
- Of all

How often are the water level/spill data evaluated for the assessment of performance?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- In near real-time
- Daily
- Once a month
- Several times a year
- Annually
- Every 5 years
- The evaluation is carried out irregularly, e.g. during the planning or revision of the integrated drainage plan
- Never

The quality of our water level monitoring data in our organization is good?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Enig
- Uenig

In our opinion, the cause of the poor data quality lies in

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Uenig' at question '20 [WLdataQlty]' (The quality of our water level monitoring data in our organization is good?)

🚫 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- The measuring instruments
- The data transmission
- The hydraulic conditions at the monitoring site

Other:

We have the following problems:

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Uenig' at question '20 [WLdataQlty]' (The quality of our water level monitoring data in our organization is good?)

🚫 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Missing measurements
- Drift in the measurement signal
- Noise on the measurement signal
- We are not sure about the accuracy of the measurements

Other:

Our organization shares the water level data with third parties ...

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

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! Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- No, we do not
- Yes, with an engineering firm to assess data quality
- Yes, to check the accuracy of our simulation models
- Yes, with local or regional regulators for compliance assessment

Other:

Is measurement technology available in your combined sewer overflows?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

The following examples describe how operators can benefit from the use of measurement technology at urban drainage systems. What are the 3 reasons that would motivate you most to use metrology?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '24 [MTavail]' (Is measurement technology available in your combined sewer overflows?)

🚫 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Making the functioning of the sewage system visible
- Costs and time savings for operating personnel
- Preservation of the value of the drainage systems
- Continuous monitoring to detect incidents
- Real-time control of wastewater systems
- Integrated management of drainage network and Wastewater Treatment Plant (and water bodies)
- Basis of assessment for future planning
- Prevention of bad investments
- Performance monitoring and performance review

Other:

Where do you see the 3 biggest obstacles to the use of measurement technology for your wastewater association?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'No' at question '24 [MTavail]' (Is measurement technology available in your combined sewer overflows?)

🗨️ Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Financial reasons
- Technical difficulties in equipping with measurement technology
- Technical difficulties in handling the measurement data
- Lack of standardized procedures
- No cantonal support for the procedure
- No legal requirements
- Metrology is not relevant or necessary for us
- We don't know much about metrology

Other:

Why did your wastewater association decide to use measurement technology on the plants? Please select a maximum of 3 main reasons.

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '24 [MTavail]' (Is measurement technology available in your combined sewer overflows?)

🚫 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

- Making the functioning of the sewage system visible
- Costs and time savings for operating personnel
- Preservation of the value of rainwater systems
- Continuous monitoring to detect incidents
- Dynamic discharge control of wastewater plants
- Integrated sewer network management of drainage network and WWTP (and water bodies)
- Basis of assessment for future planning
- Prevention of bad investments
- Performance monitoring and performance review

Other:

Do you assess the uncertainty of the collected monitoring data?
(Type A: repeated measured values, Type B: scientific judgement,
information from sensor manufacturer, Error propagation, etc)

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes, I do uncertainty calculations on my data
- No, I don't think this is needed
- No, but I would like to know more or to do this in future

Make a comment on your choice here:

Have you completed an integrated drainage plan at the level of your
wastewater association?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

In what year was this IDP approved?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '29 [IntDrainPlan]' (Have you completed an integrated drainage plan at the level of your wastewater association?)

Please write your answer here:

Is this IDP currently being revised as part of the drainage planning?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

Answer was 'Yes' at question '29 [IntDrainPlan]' (Have you completed an integrated drainage plan at the level of your wastewater association?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

How far do you agree with this statement:

Our organization cooperates well with regulatory authorities for urban drainage

Please choose **only one** of the following:

1

2

3

4

5

1= not at all

5 = completely

Have employees of your wastewater association participated in one of the following professional events within the past year?

- Trade fair (IFAT)
- National association meeting (e.g. working group meeting)
- National urban drainage conference (CIWEM, Aqua Urbanica, GRAIE, **AEOPAS**, ...)
- Event of the regulatory office in the field of urban drainage
- Customer event of engineering consultancy
- Customer event of a company related to measurement technology or automation

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
- No

Has your wastewater association already commissioned a third party (e.g. electrical or engineering consultant) to carry out the maintenance of the measurement technology (e.g. regular cleaning and calibration of measuring instruments) or to evaluate measurement data?

🗨 Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- No, neither of those
- Yes, for the maintenance of the measurement technology
- Yes, for the evaluation of the measurement data
- Yes, both for the maintenance of the measurement technology and for the evaluation of the measurement data

Do you think it makes sense for the wastewater operator to operate both the WWTP and all urban drainage systems in the long term?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- No
- Yes, it makes sense to acquire all urban drainage assets
- Yes, it makes sense to take over all stormwater systems and the regionally important sewerage system
- Yes, it makes sense to take over all rainwater systems and the entire sewerage system in the association's territory
- Other

A possible vision of the future:

"Stormwater systems and sewer networks are equipped with a large number of measuring devices. The measurement signals are transmitted live to a control system via a nationwide wireless network, automatically checked, evaluated and archived. This permanent monitoring of the systems is made possible by the advancing technological development in the areas of communication, control and automation technology."

What do you personally think of the vision described?

❗ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I am in favor of this vision and am generally open to the use of such modern technologies for the facilities of our wastewater association
- I reject this vision because I do not think much of the use of such modern technologies for the assets of our wastewater association
- I support this vision on the following condition:

Make a comment on your choice here:

Another possible vision of the future:

"In the future, monitoring data from CSOs are made publicly available on a transparent and easily accessible platform that empowers communities and stakeholders with real-time information about sewer systems and their impact on the environment. By openly sharing data on sewer infrastructure, performance, and maintenance, we aim to foster collaboration, innovation, and informed decision-making, ultimately enhancing the efficiency, sustainability, and resilience of our wastewater management practices."

What do you personally think of the vision described?

🗳️ Choose one of the following answers

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- I am in favor of this vision, because I generally find that transparency improves effectiveness and aids innovation
- I reject this vision because I think data from wastewater infrastructures should not be openly available
- I support this vision on the following condition:

Make a comment on your choice here:

Is the legal basis available for performance monitoring of CSOs (law?)

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
 No

Is a legally binding implementing ordinance/ regulation available?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
 No

Are there technical standards and guidelines available?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
 No

Are the existing regulations applied by the operator?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

- Yes
 No

Are the existing regulations are enforced by all actors?

Please choose **only one** of the following:

Yes

No

How are existing CSO structures regulated?

📌 Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

Pass forward flow to WWTW

Spill frequency

Spill volume

Water impacts

Other:

What do you think could help to promote monitoring of CSOs?

Please select 3 of the listed suggestions and assign them according to your priorities (1st, 2nd and 3rd priority). You also have the opportunity to make your own proposal.

! All your answers must be different and you must rank in order.

Please number each box in order of preference from 1 to 12

Standards and technical guidelines for equipping the systems with measurement technology (e.g. water level measuring device in the CSO)

Environmental protection targets (e.g. measured values of water level in the CSO, flow rate in the sewer)

Performance indicators

One-off subsidy for metrology equipment

Participation in the running costs of the maintenance of the measuring instruments and the evaluation of the measurement data

Better products and services from metrology companies

Customized services of engineering and design offices

Education and training opportunities for measurement technology and measurement data management

Joint events and information campaigns

Increased supervisory role of the cantons

Shifting competence from the municipality to the association

Own suggestion

Write your proposal for the question:

What do you think could help to promote monitoring of CSOs?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

----- Scenario 1 -----

Answer was 'Own suggestion' at question '44 [CSOmonit]' (What do you think could help to promote monitoring of CSOs? Please select 3 of the listed suggestions and assign them according to your priorities (1st, 2nd and 3rd priority). You also have the opportunity to make your own proposal. (RANK 1))

----- or Scenario 2 -----

Answer was 'Own suggestion' at question '44 [CSOmonit]' (What do you think could help to promote monitoring of CSOs? Please select 3 of the listed suggestions and assign them according to your priorities (1st, 2nd and 3rd priority). You also have the opportunity to make your own proposal. (RANK 2))

----- or Scenario 3 -----

Answer was 'Own suggestion' at question '44 [CSOmonit]' (What do you think could help to promote monitoring of CSOs? Please select 3 of the listed suggestions and assign them according to your priorities (1st, 2nd and 3rd priority). You also have the opportunity to make your own proposal. (RANK 3))

Please write your answer here:

Do you have any further comments or ideas on the topic of "Water protection during wet weather - organization of urban drainage" or on our questionnaire?

Only answer this question if the following conditions are met:

3

Please write your answer here:

You can optionally enter your contact information. In this way, you give us the opportunity to be available for queries. We would also be happy to inform you about the results of the survey by e-mail.

You can opt-in to apply to be part of an Co-UDLabs early adopter group of innovative utilities to share experiences regarding CSO and data management.

! Check all that apply

Please choose **all** that apply:

I want to participate in the early adopter group of innovative utilities.

Please contact me with information on further implementation actions, discuss policy suggestions, evaluate scientific developments, etc.

Thank you for taking the time to share your insights through this survey. Your input is instrumental in shaping our ongoing efforts to improve our urban drainage infrastructure and safeguard the environment. We truly appreciate your contribution.

An initial synthesis of the feedback collected will be discussed during the 2nd half of 2024.

Best regards, in the name of the Co-UDLab partners, Elodie Brelot (GRAIE) and Jörg Rieckermann (Eawag)

30.09.2024 – 22:10

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.